

- For **1a-d, 2-5**; R=Ph, R₁=H
 For **1a, 2**; R₁=Me, R₂=H
1b, 3; R₁=H, R₂=Me
1c, 4; R₁=OMe, R₂=H
1d, 5; R₁=H, R₂=OMe
1e, 6; R=Me, R₁=R₂=Cl, R₃=H
 For **2-6a**; R₄=H
b; R₄=o-Cl
c; R₄=m-Cl
d; R₄=p-Cl
e; R₄=o-OMe
f; R₄=m-OMe
g; R₄=p-OMe
h; R₄=o-Me
i; R₄=m-Me
j; R₄=p-Me

Scheme 1

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some 1-Substituted-anilinomalonyl-3,5-disubstituted- 4-substituted-phenylazopyrazoles

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Manuscript received 16 April 1991, revised 27 November 1991,
accepted 4 December 1991

PYRAZOLES have been reported to possess various biological and pharmacological activities. We have earlier synthesised some pyrazoles and evaluated their anti-HIV and anticancer activities¹. The present communication deals with the synthesis of 1-substituted-anilinomalonyl-3,5-disubstituted-4-substituted-phenylazopyrazoles by the condensation of 1,3-disubstituted-diketones with substituted-malonanilic acid hydrazides² in acetic acid medium (Scheme 1). Some of the new pyrazoles have been screened for anti-HIV, antibacterial, antitubercular, fungicidal and anticancer activities.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and elemental analyses were carried out by Carlo-Erba 1160, Thomas (CH) Coleman (N) analyser.

(2-Methyl)phenylazodibenzoylmethane (**1a**): *o*-Toluidine (2.14 g, 0.02 mol) was diazotised using aqueous HCl (16 ml; 1 : 1) and sodium nitrite (2.4 g in 6 ml water) at 0°, and the diazotised solution was added to a slurry of dibenzoylmethane (4.48 g, 0.02 mol) and sodium acetate (1.6 g in 2 ml 50% ethanol) with stirring in an ice-bath. The resulting yellow solid was recrystallised from ethanol to give **1a** (58%), m.p. 85° (Found: C, 76.92; H, 5.20; N, 7.01. C₂₂H₁₈N₂O₂ requires: C, 77.19; H, 5.26; N, 8.18%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 590 (N=N) and 1 650 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

Other compounds were prepared similarly: **1b** (66%), m.p. 80°; **1c** (38%) 55°; **1d** (48%), 60°; **1e** (49%), 111°.

1-Anilinomalonyl-3,5-diphenyl-4-(2'-methyl)phenylazopyrazole (**2a**): A mixture of (2-methyl)phenylazodibenzoylmethane (0.684 g, 0.002 mol), malonanilic acid hydrazide (0.384 g, 0.002 mol), glacial

acetic acid (6.5 ml) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (2 drops) was refluxed for 10 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed with hot acetic acid to yield **2a** (21%), m.p. 220° (Found: C, 74.23; H, 4.89; N, 13.87. $C_{31}H_{28}N_6O_9$ requires: C, 74.54; H, 5.01; N, 14.20%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (NH), 1 650 (C=O), 1 580 (N=N), 760 (aromatic ring disubstituted) and 1 320–1 460 cm^{-1} (CH_3 bend).

The other pyrazoles were prepared similarly: **2b** (23%), m.p. 270° ; **2c** (23%), 285° ; **2d** (24%), 260° ; **2e** (23%), 262° ; **2f** (24%), 290° ; **2g** (26%), 245° ; **2h** (23%), 275° ; **2i** (22%), 260° ; **2j** (24%), 262° ; **3a** (20%), 270° ; **3b** (21%), 265° ; **3c** (19%), 235° ; **3d** (22%), 270° ; **3e** (21%), 265° ; **3f** (22%), 232° ; **3g** (20%), 230° ; **3h** (25%), 285° ; **3i** (23%), 235° ; **3j** (27%), 270° ; **4a** (20%), 235° ; **4b** (14%), 240° ; **4c** (18%), 222° ; **4d** (20%), 210° ; **4e** (23%), 256° ; **4f** (14%), 270° ; **4g** (19%), 230° ; **4h** (12%), 280° ; **4i** (28%), 210° ; **4j** (14%), 265° ; **5a** (20%), 230° ; **5b** (26%), 255° ; **5c** (20%), 262° ; **5d** (18%), 255° ; **5e** (15%), 260° ; **5f** (25%), 265° ; **5g** (14%), 235° ; **5h** (26%), 282° ; **5i** (19%), 235° ; **5j** (15%), 260° ; **6a** (24%), 260° ; **6b** (40%), 232° ; **6c** (34%), 220° ; **6d** (35%), 254° ; **6e** (24%), 247° ; **6f** (28%), 245° ; **6g** (39%), 225° ; **6h** (19%), 235° ; **6i** (16%), 210° ; **6j** (13%), 230° . Compounds **2–6** were of yellow to pale yellow in colour.

Anti-HIV activity: Compounds **1a**, **1b**, **1c**, **1d**, **2c**, **2g**, **3d**, **3g**, **5c** and **5g** were screened for antiviral activity for AIDS which involved susceptible human host cells and their response was found to be 10.44, 12.99, 9.13, 11.21, 10.31, 9.62, 8.02, 10.31, 12.16 and 12.8% respectively on the infected plates.

Antitubercular activity: Compounds **1a**, **1b**, **1c**, **1d**, **2g**, **2i**, **2j**, **3i**, **3j**, **4i**, **4j**, **5b** were incorporated into Lowenstein-Jenson egg medium having concentration of 10 and 100 $g\ ml^{-1}$ and were inoculated with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* $H_{37}R_v$ strain, incubated at 37° and observed weekly for the growth of organism for eight weeks. The compounds were found to be inactive at the concentrations used.

Antibacterial activity: Compounds **2a**, **2e**, **2i**, **3a**, **3b**, **4c**, **4e**, **4h**, **6a**, **6b**, **6d**, **6f**, **6g**, **6h**, **6i** and **6j** were tested against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus albus* using cup-plate method³. The control on the infected plate was found in the range of 15–30%.

Fungicidal activity: Compounds **2b**, **3a**, **4e** and **5f** were tested by agar-plate food poisoning method⁴ in 500 and 1000 ppm concentrations (using P.D.A. medium). Plain medium was used as control. All compounds were found active against *Alternaria alternata* and *Rhizopus arrhizus*. Fungicidal activity of compounds **2b**, **3a**, **4e** and **5f** against *Alternaria alternata* was found 57, 71, 36 and 25% at concentration 500 ppm, while at 1000 ppm it was 77, 77, 46 and 43 respectively. The compounds showed respectively 62, 38, 33 and 26% activity at 500 ppm, whereas 67, 47, 24 and 47% at 1000 ppm against *Rhizopus arrhizus*.

Anticancer activity: Compounds **1a**, **1b**, **1c**, **1d**, **2c**, **2g**, **3d**, **3g**, **5c** and **5g** were tested for their anticancer activity which involved different infected cell lines (lung, colon, malonoma, ovarian, renal etc.). The compounds did not show significant anticancer activity.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Director, National Cancer Institute, Maryland, U.S.A., for anti-HIV and anti-cancer screening, Director, Tuberculosis Research Centre, Amargadh, for tuberculostatic screening, Director, D.R.D.E., Gwalior for ir spectra, R.S.I.C., Lucknow for the elemental analysis, Dr. R. P. Garg for fungicidal activity and Dean, G. R. Medical College, Gwalior for antibacterial activity. Financial assistance from MAPCOST, Bhopal for part of the research work is gratefully acknowledged. The authors express their gratitude to Principal, Government Model Science College, for facilities.

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